

Innovative Instructional Strategies in Early Childhood Education: Standpoint of Kindergarten Teachers

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Abstract. This study explored the experiences, coping mechanisms, and educational insights of kindergarten teachers implementing innovative instructional strategies. Recognizing the vital role of innovation in early childhood education, the study aimed to understand the challenges teachers face and how they navigate these challenges in the classroom. Using a qualitative research design, in-depth interviews were conducted with ten kindergarten teachers from the Laak North District in Davao de Oro. The collected data were analyzed through thematic analysis, revealing recurring patterns and emerging themes. The findings highlighted three significant experiences: constraints related to resources and technology, pressures of time and workload, and the use of creative pedagogy. To cope with these challenges, teachers employed strategies such as professional development, collaboration and peer support, and personal resilience. Additionally, they provided insights into educational management, emphasizing the need for teacher support and the importance of learner-centered innovation. Based on the results, it is recommended that educational leaders and institutions offer sustained and meaningful support to kindergarten teachers. Strengthening institutional backing is essential to empower educators to effectively adopt and implement innovative instructional strategies in early childhood settings.

KEY WORDS

1. Innovative instructional strategies 2. kindergarten teachers 3. early
childhood

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1. Introduction

The educational landscape has revolutionized to cater to diverse students' needs in a fast-paced, changing society. Influenced by technological advancements and evolving pedagogical concepts, the teaching-learning process also changed significantly. At present, instructional practices have shifted from traditional to innovative, teacher-centered to student-centered, and analog to digital. These transformative changes in learning aim to enhance student engagement and academic success. However, it is crucial

as it is challenging for many educators to adopt contemporary pedagogy, specifically in integrating the concept of innovation. Teachers are the fundamental source of instruction. However, in Hungary revealed that various educators fell behind on the latest teaching strategies and methodologies. Primary factors include lack of training and support. It prompted educators to resort to traditional teaching practices, generally applying standardized tests and rote memorization. As a result, educators are constricted

in exercising and designing meaningful learning experiences in the classroom. Additionally, these limitations hamper the confidence of educators; discouraging them from integrating innovation in teaching (Campbell-Phillips, 2020). In another study, Sharoff (2019) emphasized that internal factors heavily affect the educators' implementation of innovative instructional strategies. The study was localized in New York City. It was found that despite the intensive preparation, low self-efficacy can degrade the quality of instruction. Educators may not perform and teach well due to the overwhelming emotions and fear of failing. Thus, it also heavily affects students' learning. It may result in poor learner engagement and lowered motivation. Specifically, learners of today's generation have reduced attention span. Hence, applying instructional strategies that keep students active and engaged is indispensable. It may include using digital platforms, gamification, and creative learning activities. Similarly, in Croatia, Burić and Kim (2020) use this concern focus to emphasize how teachers are instrumental to integrating innovative instructional strategies to teaching. As discussed, some of the concerns affecting teachers in the implementation of these strategies include teacher professional development, training to implement inclusive strategies, available resources, and school support. The existence of these factors put pressure on teachers to adopt instructional practices that promotes progressive and dynamic learning environment. On the other hand, the absence of support, training, and resources results in the teacher's poor teaching ability and management skills. This may lead to poor motivation of the students and poor performance in the class. In the Philippines, the educational system continually thrives on innovative learning. Nonetheless, teachers are baffled with challenges in effectively integrating innovative instructional strategies into the teaching-learning processes. In the issue of Geronimo and Olegario (2020), found that public school teachers mostly experienced being bombarded with multiple workloads, which induce stress and exhaustion. Moreover, the demanding workplace of teachers impedes their ability to perform better at school. In some cases, teachers felt they were complying with paperwork instead of teaching students. Consequently, others lose confidence and efficacy to deliver their lesson effectively. Similarly, a study conducted by Cahapay et al. in the SOCCSKSARGEN region (2021) focused on the instructional development of kindergarten teachers amid the COVID-19 crisis. Several important issues are highlighted, such as the challenge of converting classroom activities for print modules, the development of learning resources that would address the needs of the learners, delays associated with the delivery of instructional resources, inadequate structural support for instruction, little taught parenting skills, facts harvested from assessment data having a low reliability and poor performance by the learners. These problems expose a desperate need for solutions that address the contours of a remote learning environment and reinforce the need to understand the innovative instructional approach used. The concern of Ras (2024) in the locality of Davao City, educators encounter obstacles that prevent them from pursuing innovative teaching practices. Teachers often felt inferior and insufficient to adopt new strategies, rooted in the need for more training on implementation aspects. Even the traditional classroom structures have often failed to foster playfulness with new methods, as teachers tend to worry about possible repercussions from diverting from the norm. Not embracing change can negatively impact teachers' morale, and students are stunted in their exposure to interactive, efficient instructional practices. Innovative instructional strategy is the hallmark of a progressive and life-long learning. It influences the cognition and behavior of teachers in classroom learning delivery. However,

in the local scenario of Laak North, Davao de Oro, it was observed that kindergarten teachers face challenges in integrating innovative instructional strategies in the teaching-learning process. Factors include the limited access to contemporary educational resources and continuous professional development trainings on modern technologies. These can affect the effectiveness of teachers to incorporate innovative strategies in the class. Aside from that, manag-

ing large class size has made it more difficult for teachers to provide personalized learning experiences for each student. Hence, it poses a necessity for understanding the factors that may affect the implementation of innovative strategies. Consequently, this study aims to explore the innovative instructional strategies among the kindergarten teachers in Laak North, Davao de Oro.

1.1. Purpose of the Study—The objective of this study is to investigate the innovative instructional strategies of kindergarten teachers in Laak North, Davao de Oro. The research seeks to build a foundation of understanding on the implementation of innovative instructional strategies among kindergarten teachers. Moreover, the study ventures to provide an invaluable insight to innovative instructional strategies as a contributor for an effective learning process in kindergarten. The focal point of the data collection will delve in the facets of innovative instructional strategies applied by kindergarten teachers. The result of this phenomenological study aims to contribute to the growing knowledge on innovative instructional strategies in early childhood education. Thus, the insights collected in this study can reinforce the evidence-based practices, supporting and enabling teachers to effectively integrate innovativeness in their teaching process. More so, it helps foster a learning environment that can address diverse learner needs.

1.2. Research Questions—This study aims to investigate the innovative instructional strategies of kindergarten teachers. The study will be conducted with the purpose of addressing the following inquiries:

- (1) What are the experiences of the kindergarten teachers in their implementation of innovative instructional strategies?
- (2) What are the coping mechanisms employed by the kindergarten teachers on innovative instructional strategies?
- (3) What educational management insights can be drawn from the findings of the study?

1.3. Definition of Terms—For a more comprehensive understanding, the following terms are described operationally: 1. Kindergarten Teachers. It is defined as professional educators who specialize in fostering the foundational cognitive, social, emotional, and physical development of young children, typically aged 4 to 6,

through engaging, age-appropriate instructional strategies and play-based learning (Caingcoy, 2022). 2. Innovative Instructional Strategies. It is defined as the set of interactive teaching techniques derived from new ideas and devices that can help learners increase their interest and understanding (Mahmood, 2021).

1.4. Significant of the Study—Research on instructional practices concerning innovations has practical implications for the Department of Education, school administrators, teachers, and

learners.

Department of Education Consequently, this study offers the Department of Education a chance to identify educators' professional devel-

opment requirements. The findings should help in policy and program development for improving teacher education and developing human resources for the national educational systems. Higher teacher self-efficiency is proven to affect positive learner achievement and can be said to work in tandem with the Department's goal of enhancing a highly effective education system. School Administrators The school administrators will also benefit from this study with important information to inform the effectiveness of new instructional practices from the teachers' and learners' perspective. By adopting the strategies suggested from this research, the administrators can initiate conditions for improving teachers' practices. This may result in better quality teaching and learning, better retention, and improved school performance. Teachers For teachers, this study underscores the belief on innovative practice pedagogy in their profession. It can thus provide a better understanding of how they can improve their instructional practices to make learning easier for diverse learners owing to innovation. The

1.5. Theoretical Lens—The theoretical underpinning of this study focuses on understanding the innovative instructional strategies of the kindergarten teachers in North Laak, Davo de Oro. The primary foundational theories of this exploration are the following: Social Constructivist Theory, Ecological Systems Theory, and Zone of Proximal Development Theory. This study is primarily anchored in Constructivist Theory in which theorists like Piaget (1978) posit, knowledge construction is a social process. Intrinsic to this theory, learning is presupposed to be a social process through which learners develop knowledge via their interpersonal relations with fellow learners and instructors. In the works of Piaget, it was mentioned that cognitive development significantly depends on social activities and, particularly, on language

research can also help teachers facilitate learners to embrace a growth mentality in how they tackle their lessons. Learners Another significant benefactor of this study are the learners since this study propounds the utilization of innovative instructional strategies. In other words, practical instruction through innovative instructional strategies can be positively associated with improved outcomes for kindergarten learners and their academic performances. This can lead to higher motivation levels, learning performance, and positive attitudes toward learning—which sets as a foundation on their learning journey towards primary education and beyond. Ultimately, this study can provide an additional resource to future researchers in the field of innovative instructional strategies. Thus, it also provides a substantial contribution to their academic threshold. Overall, the present research provides valuable recommendations for improving educational practice and, as well as policy, for strengthening teacher learning and fostering the learning process across multiple contexts.

meta-communication. Instead, this view emphasizes that positive social contexts and learners' interactions and communications are sources that can improve learning when organizing instruction. Contextually, the Constructivist Theory explain the need for kindergarten teachers to alter the conditions within learning environment to promote interactions. It also emphasizes the significance of incorporating new approaches to instruction that incorporate social contexts into the learning process. Through these, teachers and the learners benefit by creating more efficacy of the teaching practices among the teachers while at the same time giving better results among the learners. The study also gleans to the theory of Urie Bronfenbrenner's Ecological Systems Theory posits that human development is shaped by a network of interconnected en-

vironments. These environments range from the immediate surroundings, such as family and school, to broader societal influences. The theory identifies several layers of influence. The microsystem infers the direct interactions that influences learning. Mesosystem entails the varying connections between different environments. While, the exosystem's main concern is the indirect influences towards one's learning. Lastly, the macrosystem is about the larger cultural and societal factors. Each of these systems contributes to shaping an individual's growth and learning, emphasizing that development occurs within the context of these overlapping and dynamic environments. This framework is particularly relevant to the study of kindergarten teachers and their use of innovative instructional strategies. The microsystem focuses on the direct relationship between the teacher and child, where strategies like play-based learning are implemented. The mesosystem highlights the importance of collaboration between teachers, parents, and the school community in creating an environment conducive to innovation. The exosystem reflects factors such as professional development opportunities and resource availability, which influence a teacher's ability to adopt new teaching methods. Finally, the macrosystem, including societal attitudes toward education, either supports or restricts the integration of innovative strategies into early childhood classrooms. Together, these layers provide a comprehensive understanding of how both internal and external factors shape teaching practices in kindergarten settings. Furthermore, this study integrates Vygotsky's Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD) theory, which emphasizes the importance of guided learning within a child's developmental reach. Vygotsky (1978) defined the ZPD as the gap between what a learner can do independently and what they can achieve with the help of a more knowledgeable person, such as a teacher. This scaffolding helps learners progress by introducing challenges that are just beyond their current abilities, fostering cognitive growth and skill development. Teachers play a crucial role in providing the necessary guidance, gradually reducing their assistance as students gain proficiency. In the context of this study, Vygotsky's ZPD theory highlights how innovative instructional strategies, such as play-based and project-based learning, can facilitate development by challenging learners within their ZPD. By providing appropriate scaffolding, teachers can support children in achieving tasks they are not yet able to perform independently, thus encouraging independent learning over time. Through these strategies, teachers can promote not only cognitive development but also critical thinking and problem-solving skills. The goal of this study is to explore how teachers' application of innovative instructional strategies within the ZPD can enhance children's learning outcomes, fostering both academic growth and a love for learning. The theoretical framework for this study integrates Constructivist Theory, Ecological Systems Theory, and Zone of Proximal Development Theory to explore innovative instructional strategies of the kindergarten teachers in Laak North, Davao de Oro. The Constructivist Theory emphasizes the importance of creating a learning environment that encourages communication and collaboration, enhancing both teaching practices and student outcomes. Complementing this, the Ecological Systems Theory adds depth by illustrating how interconnected environmental factors, from direct teacher-child interactions to broader societal influences, shape a teacher's ability to implement these strategies. Finally, the ZPD theory frames the study by illustrating how teachers guide students through tasks just beyond their current abilities, fostering cognitive growth through tailored scaffolding. Together, these theories provide a comprehensive lens through which to examine innovative instructional strategies can synergistically impact learner motivation, engagement, and academic success, ultimately

Fig. 1. The Conceptual Framework of the Study

creating a more dynamic and effective learning environment. Presented in Figure 1 is the conceptual framework of the study, displaying the inclusive variables and indicators considered.

2. Methodology

In this chapter, the study’s specific objectives are effectively addressed through a detailed outline of the systematic procedures and methodologies employed in qualitative research. Additionally, the selected research design and the researcher’s roles during the study’s implementation are explained. Furthermore, the chapter provides comprehensive insights into the research subjects, clarifying their procedures and selection criteria. Finally, it delves into the techniques used for data collection, analysis, and the strategies employed to maintain ethical standards throughout the research.

2.1. Philosophical Assumptions—In qualitative research, the philosophical and qualitative assumptions set as the foundation for the research design and acts a guide for the researcher’s approach throughout the study. It includes the assumptions of ontological, epistemological, axiological, and methodological that shapes the direction of the academic investigation (Moroi, 2021). In addition, philosophical assumptions direct the researchers in their study approach, question formulation, data collection, analysis, and result interpretation.

It serves as a comprehensive framework that encompasses beliefs, methodologies, and theoretical underpinnings- forming the conceptualization and implementation of the researcher’s investigation. In this study, the chosen paradigm shaped the methodology and techniques to instill coherence throughout the study (Kamal, 2019). Ontology In this study, the dimensions of ontology explore the relationship between the problem and reality. As cited by Creswell (2013), the perceptions of reality among participants are subjective and diverse. Contextu-

ally, the realities of the existing problems on the implementation of innovative instructional strategies varies among the kindergarten teachers. Each narrative and data provided by the participants stands individually, but contributes collectively to the understanding of their overall experiences. As a researcher, my responsibility lies in integrating thematic analysis to encapsulate the diverse realities of the participants. At the same time, it enables a structure that presents a comprehensive view on the kindergarten teachers' experiences and coping mechanisms in integrating innovative instructional strategies in their teaching process. Epistemology Another philosophical assumption that focuses on the nature of knowledge is Epistemology. It infers the relationship between the knower and the known. In this assumption, the researchers pursue to bridge the gap between themselves and the participants. Through direct interaction, researchers can establish a more authentic and primary data collection process (Creswell, 2013). In this study, my role will include personally collecting data from the participants. This will allow me to engage and substantiate the information provided by the participants; in this manner I can assess not only the facts, but also the emotional and behavioral aspects that can be observed throughout the data collection process. With this, it will help understand further the subjective realities of the participants. Axiology Axiology

2.2. *Qualitative Assumptions*—Through the lens of a phenomenological research methodology, I aim to investigate the innovative instructional strategies among the kindergarten teachers in North Laak, Davao de Oro. In this qualitative framework, I intend to provide an in-depth understanding of the individual and collective significance of the variables. Moreover, I aim to uncover the unique perspectives and the elaborated details of the participants' expe-

riences. As a dedicated researcher, I seek to further surface-level observations by exploring the complexities and variations of their experiences. Thus, my goal includes the understanding of the multifaceted human experience, traversing through diverse contexts, backgrounds, and histories. In this study, in-depth interviews will be the focal priority in the data collection process. Aside from that, reflective dialogues and the analysis of the participants' narratives will is a philosophical assumption that purports the influence and significance of the researcher's values in the study. As mentioned by Creswell (2013), acknowledging and discussing values that influence the research process is imperative. The values direct the interpretation and presentation of data. In this study, the information shared by my participants will be handled with integrity and respect. Having these commitments will ensure that the findings of the study is reliable and truthfully conveyed- demonstrating the participants' individual values and the study's context. Rhetoric In research context, rhetoric entails the persuasive use of language, communication, and presentation of information. According to Beqiri (2018), the key purpose of rhetoric is to convey concepts, claims, and conclusion effectively. Thus, it aims to influence the audiences' perspectives and views about the study. In this study, I will employ an engaging and respectful narrative style as I interact with the kindergarten teachers. This will allow me to adeptly explain the study's purpose and their valuable contribution to the study, while providing participants a room to openly share their experiences and insights about the study. Moreover, this method will encourage the participants to provide unbiased, valuable contributions to better understanding the relationship that surrounds innovative instructional strategies and the kindergarten teachers.

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be emphasized. This is to explore the depths of the facets of innovative instructional strategies of kindergarten teachers in Laak North, Davao de Oro. Additionally, using the phenomenolog-

2.3. Design and Procedure—In research, choosing the right approach for a study is paramount in order to contextualize research design, data collection plan, and analysis protocol based on the objectives of the study. This study will be based on a qualitative research design. Qualitative research has been recommended as appropriate for verbal analysis, in contrast to quantitative statistical studies (Hammersley 2013). A qualitative research method is the most appropriate since my study also centered on examining the experiences, insights, and coping mechanisms of kindergarten teachers about innovative instructional strategies. Furthermore, my goal aims not to form nor refute theories, but to describe and elaborate on the phenomenon discussed in the study. Qualitative research features a range of specialized methods. It includes grounded theory, narrative analysis, case studies, phenomenology and ethnography. In this study I will use a qualitative phenomenological

2.4. Research Participants—In qualitative research, sample sizes are different from those in quantitative studies. It is important for qualitative studies to have a sample size that is sufficient to gather feedback from most, if not all, participants. Achieving saturation, where adding more participants does not provide new insights is essential. (Glaser and Strauss, 2017) support the idea of saturation as a suitable concept for determining sample size. For phenomenological studies, recommends having between 5 to 25 participants, while suggests a minimum of 6. There are no strict rules for determining the right sample size in qualitative research; it largely depends on the time, resources,

ical principles, I aim to gain a comprehensive understanding on the experiences, coping mechanisms, and educational management insights associated to innovative instructional strategies.

research design, in order to provide information concerning the understanding and experiences of participants. I used this method because phenomenology research emphasizes the well-being and strengthens appreciation of other people. Also, it highlights the viewpoints of participants, while recognizing the significance of their experiences, followed by scientific analysis of these perspectives. A phenomenological study, as defined by Creswell (2018) is an inquiry practice using the experiences of participants and attempting to explain a phenomenon in which they participated. Phenomenology aspires to clarify the interpretations of a given phenomenon into contextual descriptions that can be generalized. In this sense, my study will focus on an event that revolves around the participation of subjects in implementing innovative instructional strategies in the classroom. By collecting information directly from those with firsthand experience, I will create detailed and accurate descriptions.

and objectives. In this study, I included a total of ten (10) kindergarten teachers from North Laak, Davao de Oro. The participants will be involved in in-depth interview (IDI) to examine their personal experiences, insights, and coping mechanisms on innovative instructional strategies. Furthermore, I will employ purposive sampling in choosing the participants, wherein they are selected based on specific criteria: currently employed as a kindergarten teacher in North Laak, Davao de Oro, with teaching experience of 5 years onwards, and has no administrative case record. This type of selection method aims to ensure that they study's results are authentic and free from any biases (Creswell, 2013).

2.5. *Ethical Considerations*—Ethical considerations are an essential domain in research. It infers the moral principles and guidelines governing a researcher's conduct. Moreover, it encompasses principles that ensure responsible investigation, respectful treatment of participants, and the generation of reliable and precise information. Adhering to established ethical standards is essential for protecting participants, maintaining scientific integrity, and fostering trust within the research community. As a researcher, I will observe ethical considerations throughout the conduct of my study. There will be a systematic and ethical adherence from preparation to the actual implementation of the study, until its completion. In addition, any information released by the participants of the study will be held with utmost respect and confidentiality. Thus, every participant will be given the autonomy to decide in partaking their perspectives and insights. Social Value Social value pertains to the potential benefits and positive outcomes that a study can offer to society. It includes addressing problems and enhancing people's quality of life. In this study, the social value lies in providing the kindergarten teachers with knowledge about innovative instructional strategies. School is one of the foundations of society. Therefore, reinforcing the teaching-learning process can ripple advantages benefiting not just the stakeholders at school, but of the entire society. Informed Consent Informed consent refers to the process of obtaining the voluntary agreement to participate among the chosen participants. In this study, I will distribute a written informed consent to ask permission among the participants. They will be adequately informed about the purpose and reason for their participation, enabling them to choose whether to participate or not. It will be made clear that participants' involvement in the study will be voluntary- giving them a right to refuse to participate. Additionally, I will be cautious in ensuring the participants' psycho-

logical well-being. Written permission will be secured from the participants. I will inform them that the study aims to conduct research on the role of educational management in enhancing teacher professionalism. Vulnerability Vulnerability is the associated risk that may arise in the research process. It involves potential harm, exploitation, or coercion. Contextually, the study's respondents will be teachers, so they will not be considered vulnerable since all of them will be of legal age, and they will not be considered highly vulnerable psychologically. The researcher will emphasize that the survey will be set at the participants' convenience. Furthermore, the confidentiality of the information disclosed will be secured and protected.

Risk, Benefits, and Safety In conducting research, assessing potential risks and benefits with participants' involvement is essential. As a researcher, it is my responsibility to implement measures in safe guarding the well-being of my participants, particularly the kindergarten teachers. Consequently, in administering the survey questionnaires, I will fully disclose to the participants the nature of their participation. Additionally, the purpose and benefits of the study, as well as the confidentiality of their responses will be explained thoroughly as stated in the survey questionnaire. The participants will have the ability to ask questions related to the study without restrictions. Further, I will ensure that the participants are not subjected to harm in any way. Moreover, the questionnaire and interview guide used in this study will not contain any derogatory or unacceptable statements offensive to the participants. Likewise, this study will be designed purely to collect academic information related to the study, and they will not be asked for personal information. To minimize inconvenience, I will ensure that the respondents are given ample time to answer the survey questionnaire online. The respondents will have the freedom not to answer questions that make them feel psychological or emotional

distress. Thus, they will be free to withdraw as respondents from the study if they feel that they cannot discuss the information that is being asked of them. Ultimately, I will value their participation and place their welfare as the highest priority during the study.

Privacy and Confidentiality In research, privacy and confidentiality infers the protection for the participants' persona information. Also, it involves securing that their identities are remain confidential unless they explicitly permitted to disclose. This study will observe the Data Privacy Act of 2012. I will ensure that the data cannot be traced back to the kindergarten teachers, who are primarily the participants of the study, to protect their identities. Moreover, no personal data will be shared without the participant's consent. Thus, access to the data collected will only be exclusive to me, ensuring that no personal data will be exposed. **Justice** In research, justice is associated to the equitable distribution of the advantages and disadvantages from the diverse segments of society. To avoid impartiality in choosing the participants, I will treat all participants, the kindergarten teachers, with equal respect. There will be no implications of prejudice in choosing the participants of the study. Anyone who fits the qualifications of being an employed kindergarten teacher in Laak North, Davao de Oro in the purposively selected schools will be included. During the study, the researcher will ensure to respect the participants. As much as possible, I will schedule the survey wherein there will be minimal disruptions in the routine of the participants. To compensate for the time spent during data gathering, a token of appreciation will be given to the participants. This token will be an assortment of souvenirs. The tokens will be sent via courier, and these will be sealed carefully in a package. **Transparency** Transparency in research field refers to the integrity of the study throughout its entire phrase. Any communication concerning the research will be done

with honesty and transparency. To safeguard the welfare of the kindergarten teachers, I will implement the methods discussed in this study. All the necessary documents that support the data analysis will be included. Notably, the I will describe the extent of the participants' involvement in this study and share how I will maintain objectivity in analyzing data and presenting the results of the study. **Qualification of the Researcher** A researcher's qualifications include their educational background, work experience, and specialized knowledge in a particular area. These qualifications guarantee that the researcher has the essential skills and understanding to carry out effective research. In this study, I will ensure that other factors, such as conflict of interest, do not influence the participants' responses. The participants will have access to the findings of the study and school administrators of the participating schools. The information will be made available as long as they follow the proper protocol to protect the anonymity of the participants. Furthermore, I will also acknowledge the effort of every person who contributes to the study's success; the Division of Davao de Oro will receive a furnished copy of the research results so it can be accessed by the participants and used for learning and further study.

Adequacy of Facilities Ensuring that essential resources, tools, and infrastructure are available and appropriate is vital for conducting a study effectively and safely. Contextually, I will ensure an accessible and suitable facility, which helps in producing reliable and consistent findings while minimizing risks among the kindergarten teachers as the participants of the study. Having the right facilities allows data collection and analysis to take place. It will maintain the integrity of the research and adheres to safety standards, protecting the information of the participants. Additionally, the analysis and results gathered will be done in proficiency and alignment, serving as a primary basis for ad-

equacy. Community Involvement Community involvement involves actively involving community members, stakeholders, or the target study population at every stage of the research process. It is applied from the initial planning phase to the dissemination of results. In context, I will plan to share the findings generated with the community. Community involvement will be accorded primacy in making decisions about the research agenda, appropriate methods to apply in their context, and using the results or findings. Specifically, it aims to benefit the academic community in North Laak, Davao de Oro; sharing valuable inputs that will help enhance the teaching-learning process at schools. With this, it will further pose an understanding

on the influences that affects the learning of the learners in their community. Plagiarism and Fabrication Researchers are expected to uphold principles of academic honesty and integrity. This means giving proper credit to the work of others, making original contributions, and ensuring the accuracy and authenticity of data. In my study, I utilize plagiarism detection tools and keep thorough research documentation to guarantee that my work is free from plagiarism and that all data and findings are authentic and trustworthy. Moreso, literature and ideas from existing studies about innovative instructional strategies will be cited. By adhering to these principles will help strengthen the credibility and reliability of the research community.

2.6. Role of the Researcher—As a neutral research facilitator and advocate, it is my responsibility to make sure that the process of undertaking research does not in any way reflect my personal beliefs, be influenced by any bias or in any way influenced by any external factors. I create a culture which gives everyone permission to freely share ideas while at the same time ensuring that both the data collection and analysis processes are fair. This commitment to neutrality maintains the objectivity of the research exercise and guarantees that what is being discovered in its essence is the real phenomena of interest. As an authority in qualitative research methods, one of my primary specialties is the subject of qualitative research methods. I have read and tried such techniques as a practitioner of interviews, focus groups, and participant observations. I am proficient in skill and know-how of conducting and analyzing qualitative studies that allow comprehensive question analysis and result credibility. It makes me equipped to conduct detailed investigation of various social processes and improve the accuracy as well as the reliability of observed and described participants' experience.

As a data curator and custodian, my role is not only to collect data but also to guard and manage data. Therefore, I focus on data credibility and security; thus, I respect the rights of participants regarding privacy essentials. Organizing the data creates data's access for its subsequent examination; it strengthens the research's credibility and grants other scholars access to reliable information. Specifically, as a data analyst, I engage with the collected data to generate insights that answer the conductive research question. Using coding and thematic analysis to analyze qualitative data, I obtain recurrent and grounded insights enhancing knowledge in my field. This deep understanding of the data helps not only to derive relevant insights to be addressed, but also improves scholarly and practical discourses with regard to the study subject. Ultimately, I also assume the responsibility to synthesize and report the research results. This involves presenting to the various stakeholders the intention of the study, the methods used, the findings, and the implications in the form of reports, or any other mode. Through making my work accessible and comprehensible, I amplify the effect of these findings to serve the purpose of other

members of the academic community to embrace, replicate, and extend the knowledge and practice that has been identified here.

2.7. Data Collection—In the gathering of data, this study employed a systematic procedure. Several steps were taken in adherence to the proper data collection procedure. This was done in order to ensure the accuracy and objectivity of the data collection. Securing endorsement from the Dean of Graduate School, the Schools Division Superintendent and the School Principal As a form of protocol, the researcher will obtain permission from the necessary authorities before conducting the study. The researcher will secure a permit to use Faculty Room, Rizal Memorial Colleges, Inc. through the endorsement provided by the Dean of the Graduate School. This endorsement letter will be used to formally ask permission from the School Principals of the selected elementary schools in Laak North, Davao de Oro: Libuton Elementary School, Sisimon Elementary School, Santa Emelia Elementary School, Tugas Elementary School, and Ilpapa Elementary School. The identified participants, the kindergarten teachers in Laak North, Davao de Oro will also be informed to discuss the purpose and importance of the study, including the consent to participate. Such actions do not only guarantee that all necessary ethical standards are being met, but it also creates cooperation among all involved parties Asking Permission from the Schools Division Superintendent Once all the permissions are granted, I will proceed to request permission from the Schools Division Superintendent (SDS). This involves submitting a formal letter that outlines the research proposal's significance to the educational community. Alongside the letter, I attach Chapters 1 and 2 of my dissertation, as well as the research instrument, providing clear explanations of the study's objectives and the participant identification process. I await the SDS's response before proceeding with data collection. This proactive approach ensures that all required approvals are in place by the first two weeks of November 2024, allowing for ethical and effective research. Asking for Permission from the School Heads Thereafter, the endorsements from the relevant authorities are sought first before seeking approval from the school heads. This entails writing official letters of request to each head of the school, describing clearly the need for the research and the period that data would be collected. I will ask for the permission to conduct the study in the third week of November 2024 up to the last week of November 2024. Obtaining Consent from the Participants After consultation with the school heads, I will ask for permission from the research participants which are the kindergarten teachers. The participants will receive informed consent forms. The purpose of these forms is to describe quite comprehensively the purpose, rights and interests of participants, and type of confidentiality that a given study will uphold. Thus, it is guaranteed that all individuals are informed and willing to undertake an action with a consent of both involved parties. This consent process is planned for the end of November 2024. Conducting the Interview Once consent from all participants has been received, they will be contacted and interviews carried out at an appropriate time. To maintain credibility and validity in the study, structured or semi structured interview schedule will be employed. These interviews are planned to be held in the first half of December 2024. Transcribing the Responses of the Interviewees Following the interview sessions, the answers given by the participants will be transcribed carefully by me. It involves the actual conversion of the data into text that is not limited to word of mouth but also emphasizes on accompa-

nying paraverbal phenomena and contextually relevant details. To capture all these reactions in detail, I will record the participant based on

audio and also take notes in the field. Transcription work is planned on third week of December of year 2024.

2.8. *Data Analysis*—After data collection the next step that will be carried out is data coding and thematic content analysis. This systematic process includes sorting of transcribed data where it is grouped into categories, sub-categories, and themes according to dialogues from interviews. Thus, I analyze the relationships within the collected data and make conclusions resulting in beneficial insights that are closely connected to the aims and goals of the research. It guarantees that the findings are as close as possible to recount of the participants' accounts. For this study, I employ Creswell's Thematic Analysis approach that is most appropriate in compiling participants' feedback with the promise of containing diversified thematic representations. Thematic analysis confirms the portrayal of individual aspects by the participants and helps to categorize the shown patterns of the observed responses. Used as a qualitative research approach, thematic analysis allows the researcher to systematically categorize and analyze data. It concerns the processes of finding

out general patterns into which subordinates of a study are grouped. This process involves the use of careful analysis and re-analysis of the transcriptions until one is very sure that they have understood the data fully as envisaged in the objectives of the study. In my study, I choose Creswell's Thematic Analysis which includes several crucial stages. Initially, I will analyze the data, getting to know it inside out. Then, the data will be classified semantically and divided according to two different parameters regarding the numerous part components. For this, I will develop themes that would provide the essence of the set objectives as they captured the database. Each theme will be described and named in order to enhance understanding of essential principles. Lastly, I will provide a conclusion in the form of a paper, where I merged the overall concerns into neatly wrapped article that would generate the understanding of the conclusion of the study. This systematic approach enables coverage of your subject of interest and thus our understanding is advanced.

2.9. *Framework of Analysis*—In the present research study, I will use Colaizzi's method as the approach to analysis, interpretation, and presentation of data. It will allow the assessment of the participants' experiences and perceptions towards innovative instructional strategies within interviews and dialogue sessions. More importantly, Colaizzi described a phenomenological method that expounds a precise seven step approach to data analysis. This approach unleashes the generation of a brief but detailed description of the studied phenomenon, as endorsed by individuals who experienced the phenomenon under consideration. Hear

how it is depends on qualitative descriptions and that the ways of data gathering consist of face-to-face, written accounts, blogs, research diary, and online interviews. It was found that using Colaizzi's method enables the identification of emergent themes and analysis of the relationships between various aspects within data.

Data Familiarization During the data familiarization phase aimed at getting more comfortable with the transcripts, I will look through the data several times to grasp the intentions behind the participants' actions. Such a thorough analysis is important to understand even the details

of their statements and to make a good further analysis of their experiences. Identifying Significant Statements During data analysis, I will pay a lot of attention to the selection of all the statements in the provided narratives that can be connected to the investigated phenomenon in one or other way. When using explicit and often quantitative analysis such as written case; narratives or transcripts of interviews. I will underscore some of the phrases and descriptions that reflect the situations of the participants. This step helps me to track down the specific elements I am comparing, thus keeping my analysis rigorous; as well as relevant for defining themes. Formulating Meanings During the formation of meanings, I will look at the key statements necessary for the topic and answer whether they relate to the given phenomenon. It may not be possible to fully bracket my existence as a phenomenologist, as Colaizzi has recommended, but I attempt to bracket off my own presuppositions and patterns of interpretation. This helps to maintain the variance on the basis of the participants' experiences as closely as possible. Clustering Themes When determining the themes of meaning for the analysis, I will strictly cluster the meanings that fit into general themes that the subjects demonstrate. In doing so, I must continually remind myself of the idea of 'bracketing' or eliminating prior knowledge and experience thus averting the situation where the research becomes skewed by a certain theory. It becomes important to avoid forcing identifiable themes on the data because this would distort the analysis. Developing an Exhaustive Description In the final step, I will

write a paragraph where all the themes produced from the prior analysis are reconceptualized and captured in an all-inclusive account. Such broad term and characterization are employed with the intention to describe the phenomenon as broad and complex. Reiterating this, to facilitate the final representation and guarantee that the main concerns of each partaker are encompassed, I will analyze accounts for recurrent themes only.

Producing the Fundamental Structure In the last process of the procedure, I will develop an exhaustive description encompassing all themes identified in the above analysis. Such conventional and exhaustive definition is used with the purpose to give the impression of the phenomenon and its multifaceted nature. Through aggregating the regularities of the themes from part and parcels of participants' disclosure, their misconception is systematically incorporated and reflected in the final representation. Seeking Verification of the Fundamental Structure During the verification step, I will ask participants whether the statement proposed within the frame of the basic structure statement corresponds to the participants' experience or not. This means that the statement is given back to all participants or, in some larger studies, to a sample subset. This process increases validity and reliability of conclusions which remain strong within participants' voices. The following figure also shows this intensive process, and underscores each of the steps in order to provide a clear picture of the actions that were carried out to analyze the data in as comprehensive a manner as possible.

2.10. Trustworthiness of the Study—The trustworthiness of a study deals with the extent to which the findings can be considered reliable, logical and genuine. Thus, it seeks to present that the study's conclusions are valid. In qualitative research, human quality indicators which

include credibility, transferability, confirmability, and dependability are often utilized to assess the study's reliability. Credibility In establishing credibility, there is need to provide evidence that the results obtained indeed portrays the true experiences of kindergarten teachers in imple-

Fig. 2. Analytical Framework of the Study

menting innovative instructional strategies. In an effort to establish credibility, I will spend a considerable amount of time talking with participants and wrap it with clear understanding. Also, I will use triangulation whereby data is obtained through respondents' observation, interviews, and administration of questionnaires. In order to enhance the credibility of the interpretations, I will offer the kindergarten teachers a draft of the results for checking. Transferability Generalizability is the concept describing the possibility to use the results of study in other conditions or with other people. It will help provide a clear general finding that is closely connected with the status of the teaching strategies of kindergarten teachers in a particular educational setting. At the same time, it is important to give detailed renditions of research context as well as the methodology of the study. The actual strength of the study is that the narrative provided by the participants will make it easier for educators, school administrators, and researchers to judge the extent to which the findings of the research can be transferable to similar settings or populations. By following these guidelines, the study can also provide

dependable and accurate data results with respect to the kindergarten teacher perspectives on innovative instructional strategies. It can also raise the study's relevance and influence among academic professionals, while offering practical suggestions for further examination and teaching design. Confirmability Confirmability helps to attain research impartiality since the research findings are informed by the participants and not by my prejudices. Extensive documentation will be kept, of what method was used to collect the data to the decisions that were made during the analysis. This is an advantage because other researchers can assess the health of the study's objectivity based on the decisions made during the development of the method.

Dependability Dependability proves that the results obtained in a study are recoverable in another similar context. I uphold dependability by being very careful with the whole research process, right from data collection technique to data analysis procedures. These documents will prove the study's reliability; reflecting the explicit adherence to ethical and logical considerations throughout the entire research process.

3. Results and Discussion

In this chapter, the study presents the research questions and the answers extracted from the responses of the participants. This part of the study uncovers the experiences, coping mechanisms and lessons learned from the kindergarten teachers in implementing innovative instructional strategies. The emerging themes for the experiences of the kindergarten teachers are resource and technology constraints, time and workload challenges, and creative pedagogy. On the other hand, the coping mechanisms include professional development, collaboration and peer support, and resilience. Ultimately, the themes for educational management insights are additional teacher support and integration of innovative technology.

3.1. Experiences in Implementing Innovative Instructional Strategies of Kindergarten Teachers —In the classroom, teachers often face the challenge of finding new ways to keep young learners engaged and motivated. They work to create learning experiences that are both

meaningful and enjoyable, especially in early childhood settings. Through daily routines and interactions, some teachers try fresh approaches that move beyond traditional methods. Their stories reflect a combination of excitement, trial and error, and thoughtful reflection. While some

feel encouraged by the progress they see in their learners, others express concerns about time limits, lack of resources, or unclear support. The first research question reveals the

3.1.1. Resource and Technology Constraints—In many early childhood classrooms, the commitment to creative and engaging teaching often meets the limits of what is available. Teachers imagine lessons that use music, movement, stories, and digital tools- bringing ideas to life. However, their plans sometimes shift when the materials or technology they need are deficient. These quiet moments of adjustment, where ideas are reshaped to fit what is at hand, offer a glimpse into the daily realities of teaching. Beneath the surface of enthusiasm lies a steady negotiation between what teachers hope to do and what their environment allows. The findings are aligned with the study of Yang and Hong (2022), where there is a growing demand for innovative instructional in early childhood education that is often complicated by limited access to resources and technology. It further highlights that while teachers are encouraged to embrace instructional strategies that are in sync with 21st-century skills, many face challenges in doing so due to a lack of training and essential tools. This mismatch between expectations and support restricts what teachers can offer in the classroom. At the same time, it contributes to stress and feelings of inadequacy. As the pressure to innovate increases, the absence of proper guidance and materials can leave educators caught between ambition and reality. In a similar vein, Taimur et al. (2021) found that many teachers question the practicality of implementing innovative strategies in real-world settings. Their study reveals that time limitations, minimal professional development, and a lack of classroom resources are persistent barriers that prevent meaningful change. Teachers in underfunded schools or those managing

experiences- challenges, personal commitment, creativity, and the school environment all play a role in shaping how new strategies take root.

large groups of young learners tend to find it challenging to move beyond basic instructional methods. Despite their interest in trying new approaches, the daily demands of the job and the conditions in which they work often force them to make compromises. This tension reflects how structural challenges can shape and sometimes restrict a teacher's ability to bring new ideas into practice. Adding to the discussion on resource and technology constraints, (Cohen-Vogel et al., 2020) emphasize that teachers also face challenges when innovative strategies do not fully align with the developmental needs of young learners. In many cases, the lack of appropriate tools or training makes it difficult to adapt modern methods in ways that suit early childhood settings. As a result, some educators choose to blend traditional and innovative practices to bridge the gap in resources and ensure that lessons remain age-appropriate. This careful balancing act reflects how teachers adjust their strategies based on what is both available and practical in their teaching environment. Further supporting this theme, Jackson (2023) highlights that while innovative instructional strategies offer many potential benefits, their implementation is often limited by a lack of access to essential resources. This issue is especially pronounced in underfunded schools, where teachers may not have the technological tools, learning materials, or manipulatives needed to carry out creative approaches. In addition to material shortages, practical concerns such as cramped classroom spaces and high student-to-teacher ratios create further obstacles. These conditions make it difficult to organize activities that rely on movement, collaboration, or hands-on learning, thereby limiting the full integration of in-

novative methods into daily practice. Similarly, Denia and Fahriany (2020) found that kindergarten teachers often approach innovative strategies with caution due to practical limitations in their work environment. A lack of resources, minimal training opportunities, and time constraints continue to shape how willing and able teachers are to adopt new methods. Additionally, concerns also arise around the sustainability of strategies that depend on technology or frequent updates, which may not be feasible in all settings. These findings underscore the need for consistent support systems that equip teachers with the tools and knowledge necessary to overcome these challenges and apply innovation in a way that is both effective and lasting. The studies reviewed reveal a consistent pattern of challenges faced by kindergarten teachers

3.1.2. *Time and Workload Challenges* —

In the daily flow of kindergarten classrooms, teachers manage a range of responsibilities that extend beyond instruction. They attend to the academic, social, and emotional needs of young learners while also meeting administrative and institutional expectations. These ongoing demands often leave little room for planning or implementing new teaching approaches. As a result, the pace and structure of their workday can influence how they engage with innovation and manage their professional tasks. This context provides insight into the challenges teachers face as they balance multiple roles within limited time frames. The study of Taimur et al. (2021) underscores that time constraints are a significant barrier for teachers attempting to implement innovative strategies. Alongside limited training and resources, many educators report that the fast-paced nature of their workday leaves little opportunity to explore or apply new approaches. It is particularly evident in underfunded schools or classrooms with high student-to-teacher ratios, where teachers must prioritize basic instructional tasks and classroom manage-

ment. In these settings, even motivated educators find it challenging to shift from routine practices, as the demands of their workload often outweigh the time needed for innovation. Additionally, Li (2021) emphasizes that time constraints also hinder kindergarten teachers from adopting innovative strategies. The need to meet curriculum standards and achieve set learning outcomes often restricts the time available for creative or exploratory teaching methods. Teachers frequently find themselves caught between the demands of structured schedules and the importance of allowing children time for play and discovery. Balancing these expectations requires thoughtful planning and adaptability, yet classroom management challenges and administrative tasks often limit such flexibility. These conditions further complicate teachers' efforts to implement innovative practices in meaningful ways. Similarly, Denia and Fahriany (2020) found that time constraints, alongside limited resources and training, contribute to teachers' cautious approach toward implementing innovative strategies. Many educators are hesitant to fully adopt new methods when they

are unsure whether these can be maintained over time, especially those that depend on frequent updates or advanced technology. The uncertainty surrounding the long-term feasibility of such strategies adds to the existing pressures of time-bound instructional schedules and daily classroom responsibilities. These findings reinforce the need for consistent support systems that allow teachers to manage their workload while exploring innovation with greater confidence. Undheim and Ploog (2024) further highlight that while innovative instructional strategies offer clear benefits, their implementation in kindergarten settings is often met with practical challenges. Time constraints, limited access to technology, and insufficient professional development create significant barriers to full integration. Teachers may also face external pressures from cultural norms and parental expectations that favor traditional teaching methods, which can discourage experimentation with newer approaches. These factors contribute to a work environment where innovation is chal-

3.1.3. Creative Pedagogy —In the dynamic environment of early childhood education, kindergarten teachers continually explore new ways to engage and inspire their students. The integration of innovative instructional strategies has become a vital aspect of fostering creativity and enhancing the learning experience. Despite the setbacks experienced by the teachers in resources and time preparation, many have embraced implementing innovative strategies as a creative pedagogy to cultivate an engaging and adaptive learning environment. Through their experiences, educators have implemented various strategies that promote curiosity, critical thinking, and a sense of agency among young learners. This shift toward creative pedagogy highlights the resilience and resourcefulness of teachers as they adapt their methods to meet the diverse needs of their students. In connection with this theme, several

studies support the role of creative pedagogy in enhancing the experiences of teachers as they implement innovative instructional strategies. Sharoff (2019), in a study conducted in New York City, emphasized that internal factors significantly shape how teachers carry out new instructional methods. Even with extensive preparation, educators with low self-efficacy may experience fear and emotional stress, which can lower the quality of instruction. These internal struggles often affect learner engagement and motivation, especially in classrooms where learners have shorter attention spans. Prince (2023) further supports this perspective by emphasizing the value of higher-order thinking in the classroom. Strategies that involve inquiry and problem-solving help learners engage more deeply with content and develop critical and creative thinking skills. When teachers encourage learners to analyze, evaluate, and create, they

foster intellectual curiosity and exploration. It aligns closely with the goals of creative pedagogy, which seeks to create more meaningful and dynamic learning experiences. The importance of creativity in teaching is also emphasized by Kalyani and Rajasekaran (2018), who noted that creative instructional strategies support learner engagement by allowing learners to explore, experiment, and express their ideas. These strategies often involve the use of the arts, differentiated instruction, and approaches tailored to various learning styles. Creating a classroom environment that encourages original thinking. Hence, learners become more motivated and involved in their learning. Moreover, Lian (2018) highlighted that fostering a creative learning environment requires teachers to take on new roles and step beyond their comfort zones. Being open to change and willing to serve as facilitators or co-learners allows teachers to respond to learner's needs more effectively. This adaptability helps build a space that supports collaboration and creativity, leading to improved learning outcomes. Finally, creating a democratic classroom environment is essential to sustaining creativity. Dörnyei and Muir (2019) pointed out that learners who feel respected and included are more willing to par-

ticipate and express their ideas. This sense of belonging encourages them to engage in collaborative work and explore different perspectives. In such environments, teachers can introduce varied resources and learning activities that foster both creativity and critical thinking. These findings reinforce that creative pedagogy enriches the teaching experience and supports the holistic development of learners in early education settings. Overall, creative pedagogy is a significant part of teachers' experiences in implementing innovative instructional strategies. It reflects their ability to adapt, explore new approaches, and create engaging learning environments despite challenges such as limited resources or emotional strain. Through creativity, teachers design lessons that promote curiosity, critical thinking, and active participation among young learners. This approach is not limited to the use of new tools or methods. However, it extends to fostering a classroom atmosphere where learners feel encouraged to express ideas and take part in meaningful activities. The practice of creative pedagogy reveals the resilience and dedication of educators who continuously seek to enhance learning by making instruction responsive, inclusive, and inspiring.

3.2. Coping Mechanisms in Implementing Innovative Strategies—Teachers across various disciplines and educational levels regularly face complex demands when trying to bring fresh and engaging methods into their classrooms. Particularly in kindergarten, the process of innovation brings both excitement and uncertainty,

requiring teachers to find ways to adapt and persevere. Such efforts help them manage the pressures that come with change and maintain a sense of purpose in their work. Through such strategies, teachers find ways to sustain their enthusiasm and continue fostering meaningful learning experiences for their learners.

3.2.1. Professional Development—Teachers constantly seek growth as they respond to the evolving needs of their learners and the demands of modern education. In this journey, professional development becomes a vital part

of their teaching experience. It offers opportunities not just to acquire new skills but also to deepen understanding, reflect on practice, and stay connected with current trends. Whether through formal training, workshops, or infor-

Fig. 3. Experiences in Implementing Innovative Instructional Strategies of Kindergarten Teachers

mal learning communities, these experiences shape how educators approach their roles. As they continue to grow professionally, they become more confident and equipped to bring innovation and relevance into their classrooms. Professional development is a vital aspect of enabling teachers to implement innovative instructional strategies in their classrooms effectively. As Agbaria (2021) points out, one of the significant challenges kindergarten teachers faces is the lack of adequate support and professional development opportunities. Many educators feel unprepared to use new teaching methods due to insufficient training, which affects their confidence and willingness to experiment with innovation. This lack of preparation is compounded by limited access to necessary resources, such as technology and teaching materials, which further complicates the adoption of effective practices. Without these essential supports, teachers may struggle to integrate innovative strategies into their teaching, leading to inconsistent or ineffective results. In line with this, Romero-Tena et al. (2020) highlight the need for more targeted training, particularly in using technology and other innovative instructional approaches. Early childhood educators often report feeling underprepared to incorporate modern techniques into their classrooms, which underscores the importance of professional development that is specifically tailored to current educational demands. This gap in training can create significant barriers, preventing teachers from fully realizing the potential of innovative strategies. As a result, the lack of proper professional development can hinder both the quality of teaching and the overall learning experience for students. While the implementation of innovative strategies presents challenges, it is clear that these methods can bring substantial benefits when executed effectively. According to Aguilar (2024), teachers who embrace innovative practices report improvements in student engagement, critical thinking, and collaboration. However, balancing innovation with traditional methods is equally important to ensure that new strategies remain developmentally appropriate and sustainable. Therefore, continuous professional development, collaboration among teachers, and a supportive teaching environment are crucial for overcoming barriers and fostering an atmosphere where innovation can thrive. Furthermore, as demonstrated in the study by Burić and Kim (2020), teachers play a central role in integrating innovative strategies. Nevertheless, their ability to do so is heavily influenced by the professional development and resources available to them. When teachers lack training and support, their teaching effectiveness and classroom management skills may suffer, resulting in lower student motivation and performance. It highlights the need for a well-rounded approach to professional development, one that equips teachers with the knowledge, skills, and resources necessary to implement innovative strategies successfully. In conclusion, while challenges exist, providing teachers with comprehensive support systems is essential for the successful integration of innovation in early childhood education. Professional development plays a key role in helping educators gain the skills and confidence necessary to implement innovative instructional strategies in their classrooms. The importance of modern instructional methods is widely acknowledged. However, many teachers face significant challenges in applying these approaches effectively due to insufficient training and limited access to resources. Hence, for teachers to successfully adopt and sustain new teaching methods, professional development is deemed comprehensive. It provides the right balance between traditional practices and innovative strategies that align with current educational needs.

3.2.2. *Collaboration and Peer Support—*

In the dynamic and evolving landscape of education, the role of collaboration and peer support emerges as a critical factor in fostering both personal and professional growth. Within the context of innovative instructional strategies, particularly in the early years of education, teachers are increasingly finding strength in shared experiences and mutual learning. The collaborative spirit among educators not only enhances the effectiveness of teaching methods but also nurtures a sense of community that supports the ongoing development of individual teaching practices. As educators navigate the complexities of implementing creative pedagogies, peer support becomes an essential cornerstone, offering a network of resources, advice, and encouragement. This collective approach to professional growth speaks to the power of shared knowledge and the impact it can have on the learning environment. The findings of the study corroborate the importance of collaboration and peer support in enhancing the use of technology in the classroom. As teachers integrate digital tools such as interactive whiteboards, educational apps, and online platforms, they frequently rely on collaboration with colleagues to optimize these resources effectively. This peer support allows for the exchange of strategies and solutions, contributing to a more vigorous learning environment. Similar to the research by Mahmood (2021), which emphasizes that technology promotes collaboration among learners, the findings suggest that when educators work together, they can foster a community that benefits both teachers and students. By sharing experiences and insights, teachers are better equipped to address challenges, ultimately creating a more engaging and supportive learning experience that encourages critical skills like digital literacy and collaboration. In addition to the integration of technology, the courage and adaptability of educators play a pivotal role in fostering a collaborative learning environment. Lian (2018) emphasizes that this willingness to adapt enables educators to respond to students' evolving needs in real-time. By taking on roles such as facilitators or mentors, teachers model a collaborative mindset that encourages creativity, critical thinking, and exploration. These qualities enhance the learning experience and create a culture of support and mutual respect among both teachers and learners. As teachers embrace these innovative approaches, they contribute to the growth of a dynamic, creative, and collaborative classroom atmosphere. Moreover, collaboration among teachers is critical for ensuring that teaching practices align with the latest pedagogical advancements. Keeping up with modern teaching methods, such as project-based learning and experiential education, helps teachers craft engaging lessons that encourage learners to think creatively. Bloom and VanSlyke-Briggs (2019) argue that such strategies promote the development of key skills, including collaboration and communication. When teachers collaborate to refine these approaches, they create opportunities for learners to engage in meaningful, hands-on experiences that enhance both their academic and social skills. By pooling resources, knowledge, and expertise, educators can create a supportive network that strengthens the impact of innovative instructional strategies. In parallel with these teacher collaborations, it is essential to recognize the role of social learning in a creative classroom. The cooperative learning strategies used by teachers help develop vital social skills in learners, such as teamwork, communication, and empathy. Research by Le et al. (2018) suggests that collaborative teaching methods lead to better learner outcomes by fostering social interaction and cooperative problem-solving. This collaborative approach extends beyond the classroom as teachers work with parents and other stakeholders to create a supportive learning community. By emphasizing the importance of social skills and providing students with opportunities to interact and

collaborate, educators create a learning environment where learners feel valued and connected. However, the challenges of implementing innovative instructional strategies should not be overlooked. Jackson (2023) underscores the difficulties faced by kindergarten teachers, particularly those working in underfunded schools, in accessing the resources necessary to support creative pedagogies. Limited access to technology, classroom materials, and physical space can impede the effective implementation of collaborative and hands-on activities. Despite these challenges, the benefits of collaboration and peer support remain clear. By working together to overcome logistical barriers, teachers can continue to provide meaningful learning experiences that promote both academic success and social development. In summary, the findings emphasize that collaboration and peer

support are key to effectively integrating technology into the classroom. When teachers work together, they can share strategies and resources, making it easier to navigate the challenges of using digital tools. This collaborative approach fosters a more engaging and supportive environment, encouraging the development of important skills like digital literacy and critical thinking. Furthermore, teachers who embrace innovative methods and adapt to new roles help create a classroom atmosphere that nurtures creativity and exploration. While challenges such as limited resources exist, the study highlights the importance of continued collaboration to overcome these barriers, ensuring that teaching strategies remain practical and accessible. Ultimately, collaboration and peer support not only enhance teaching but also contribute to a more inclusive and dynamic learning environment.

3.2.3. Resilience—the teaching profession relies heavily on resilience, particularly for kindergarten educators who work in a dynamic and often challenging environment. In the early stages of a child's education, teachers face the responsibility of fostering not only academic growth but also emotional and social development. The nature of early childhood education requires teachers to be flexible and resourceful, balancing the needs of diverse learners while managing the demands of the classroom. As they face daily challenges, resilience enables teachers to persevere and maintain their commitment to providing a supportive learning environment. In this context, resilience becomes a crucial trait that empowers educators to thrive and inspire their students, ensuring that they can adapt, grow, and overcome obstacles in their professional journeys. The capacity of kindergarten teachers to adopt and sustain innovative instructional strategies is strongly tied to their resilience in the face of internal and external challenges. As Sharoff (2019) highlights, inter-

nal factors, particularly low self-efficacy, can significantly undermine educators' ability to implement new methods effectively. Even with adequate preparation, teachers may struggle due to emotional stress and fear of failure, which can lead to reduced instructional quality and hinder student engagement. It emphasizes the need for resilient dispositions among teachers, allowing them to manage self-doubt and emotional strain while maintaining commitment to pedagogical innovation. Without resilience, the pressure to perform can impair both teaching and learning, especially given the short attention spans and diverse needs of today's young learners. Resilience becomes more evident when kindergarten teachers persevere in applying strategies that require adaptation and creativity despite various classroom demands. Yin et al. (2021) report that when teachers implement differentiated instruction, it enhances student outcomes and experience professional fulfillment. This sense of accomplishment contributes to their psychological stamina and reinforces their ca-

capacity to continue navigating pedagogical challenges. The ability to tailor learning while managing complexity in diverse classrooms is a direct reflection of a teacher’s resilience. Rather than retreating in the face of instructional difficulties, resilient educators continue to reflect, adapt, and improve their approaches. Teachers’ outlooks on innovation, as explored in the study by Undheim and Ploog (2024), often reveal a balance between enthusiasm and caution. Many teachers express optimism regarding the potential of innovative strategies to enrich student learning, but they are also aware of the practical challenges involved. It is here that resilience serves as a coping mechanism- helping educators sustain enthusiasm while managing realistic concerns about implementation. For example, when teachers face setbacks related to student readiness, lesson pacing, or classroom management, their resilience allows them to recalibrate instead of abandoning their efforts. This balancing act between hope and hesitation is shaped by a teacher’s ability to emotionally and cognitively process obstacles without losing sight of long-term goals. Furthermore, resilience is essential when dealing with structural barriers to innovation. Denia and Fahriany (2020) found that resource limitations, lack of training, and time constraints often hinder teachers. These systemic issues can dissuade teachers from adopting new strategies unless they possess the resilience to advocate for support and

make creative use of what is available. Teachers who are able to persist despite such constraints demonstrate a form of resilience grounded in problem-solving and advocacy. This tenacity enables them to continue delivering high-quality instruction, even in less-than-ideal conditions and helps them maintain the motivation to pursue professional growth. Meanwhile, the importance of a flexible mindset, a key component of resilience, is reflected in the findings of Veraksa et al. (2023), where teachers advocate for a blended approach to teaching. Rather than viewing innovation and tradition as mutually exclusive, resilient teachers are capable of integrating both to meet the developmental needs of their students. This adaptability allows them to shift strategies as needed, responding to classroom dynamics without becoming overwhelmed. The willingness to adjust rather than abandon reflects a durable commitment to student learning. It underscores how resilience supports both the continuity and creativity of instructional practices in early childhood education. Ultimately, resilience enables kindergarten teachers to cope with the emotional, practical, and instructional challenges of implementing innovative instructional strategies. It allows them to adapt to limited resources, manage self-doubt, and balance modern and traditional methods, ensuring they remain effective and responsive to their students’ diverse needs.

3.3. Educational Management Insights in Implementing Innovative Instructional Strategies —Managing a classroom is never easy, especially in kindergarten, where every child

learns differently. Teachers are expected to make learning fun, meaningful, and engaging. However, behind every successful classroom is a system that supports and guides teachers in trying new ways to teach.

3.3.1. Additional Teacher Support — Teaching in kindergarten is both rewarding and challenging, as young children require creative

and engaging ways to learn. Teachers are often expected to introduce new strategies that capture attention and support early development.

Fig. 4. Coping Mechanisms in Implementing Innovative Instructional Strategies of Kindergarten Teachers.

However, these efforts are difficult to sustain without proper support and guidance. School leaders play a vital role in helping teachers bring innovation into the classroom by providing clear direction, necessary resources, and opportunities for growth. This leads us to the first theme, which highlights educational management insights in implementing innovative instructional strategies. Collaborative learning, as an innovative teaching strategy, has proven to be an effective tool in enhancing student engagement and academic performance. Similar to the study of Al-Husseini et al. (2021), it highlights the benefits of collaborative learning, which encourages peer interaction and shared problem-solving. This strategy has been shown to improve academic performance and interpersonal skills among students. However, for collaborative learning to be successful, teachers need adequate support. They must be equipped with the necessary resources, professional development, and guidance to foster such learning environments. Without sufficient administrative backing, teachers may face challenges in implementing collaborative strategies effectively, thereby limiting the potential for positive student outcomes. Ensuring that teachers receive the proper support is essential for the successful adoption of this innovative teaching method. In their study, Ortile and Garcia (2023) emphasize the importance of administrative support in the successful implementation of innovative instructional strategies, particularly in a senior high school context in Sorsogon. They found that factors such as insufficient infrastructure, lack of funding, and limited professional development hinder the effective adoption of new teaching methods. It is particularly problematic in diverse classrooms, where both external factors like students' home backgrounds and internal factors such as emotional conditions can impact learning outcomes. Adequate administrative support, including resource allocation and teacher training, is critical to overcoming these barriers and enabling teachers to engage their students through innovative instructional strategies. Comparably, Le et al. (2018) argue that collaboration among teachers is essential for improving educational outcomes. By sharing strategies, resources, and insights, teachers can create more inclusive and effective learning environments. This collaborative approach not only strengthens teacher practices but also enhances social learning opportunities for students. For collaboration to be successful, teachers must first receive the necessary support and training. Without proper resources and professional development, teachers may struggle to work together effectively. Therefore, schools need to provide the support that fosters a culture of collaboration among educators, benefiting both teachers and students. In the same vein, Okada and Matsuda (2019) stress the importance of social skills development in early childhood education. They argue that fostering empathy, cultural awareness, and effective social interactions should be central to innovative teaching practices. Teachers need support in developing and implementing strategies that promote social learning, such as strong classroom management and attention to non-verbal cues. When educators are equipped with the right tools and training, they can create environments that nurture these critical social skills, preparing students to thrive in a collaborative and interconnected world. It emphasized the need for ongoing professional development and administrative backing to ensure that teachers can effectively integrate social learning into their classrooms. On the other hand, the finding is supported by the study of Dewi et al. (2020), which focuses on the significance of teacher-student interactions in early childhood education, noting that responsive and supportive teaching practices directly influence students' academic and social development. For teachers to implement such practices effectively, they must be provided with the necessary training

and resources. Without adequate professional development, teachers may lack the confidence or skills needed to adapt their teaching methods to meet the diverse needs of their students. As a result, providing teachers with the support they need to engage with innovative teaching strategies is crucial to fostering positive developmental outcomes in young learners. Implementing innovative strategies in kindergarten classrooms comes with many challenges, including limited

resources, time constraints, and diverse learner needs. Teachers often feel unprepared or overwhelmed without proper guidance and tools. To address these difficulties, consistent support in the form of training, collaboration, and accessible resources is necessary. With the proper support, teachers are more confident and capable of applying creative methods that enhance learning and engagement.

3.3.2. Learner-centered Innovation— Classrooms today are changing, and technology is becoming a key part of how young children learn. In kindergarten, using innovative technology helps make lessons more engaging, interactive, and suited to the needs of modern learners. From educational apps to digital storytelling, these tools can capture children’s attention and support their development. This directs us to the second theme, which is learner-centered innovation. The second emerging theme centers on learner-centered innovation, which highlights how progressive instructional strategies can transform the educational experience for young learners. Estrella et al. (2022) emphasize that in kindergarten classrooms, fostering engagement, creativity, and exploration is vital for holistic development. To achieve this, innovative approaches such as play-based learning, project-based learning, and technology integration become essential. These strategies not only cater to the diverse needs of children but also create environments rich in curiosity and discovery, ultimately laying the groundwork for lifelong learning. In line with this perspective, Duncan (2024) illustrates the significant advantages of play-based learning in enhancing both academic and social skills. His research indicates that when teachers purposefully incorporate play into lessons, children demonstrate increased engagement, improved retention of concepts, and enhanced interpersonal interactions. More-

over, the integration of digital play through educational apps and virtual simulations further supports this learner-centered approach by fostering collaboration and critical thinking in an interactive, enjoyable setting. Transitioning from the benefits of play, Mahmood (2021) highlights the transformative role of technology-enhanced instruction in promoting access to information and collaboration among learners. His findings reveal that digital tools, such as interactive whiteboards and educational applications, cultivate engaging and dynamic learning environments tailored to the diverse needs of students. Through these innovative methods, children not only become more engaged but also develop essential 21st-century skills, such as digital literacy and critical thinking, which are crucial for success in a technology-driven society. Building on this theme, Vásquez-Pajuelo et al. (2024) focus specifically on how ICT contributes to developing students’ abilities to access and evaluate information responsibly. Their research indicates that technology fosters independent information gathering and teaches critical evaluation skills. By guiding students in these areas, teachers not only promote active learning but also help them cultivate the essential competencies needed for success in the digital age. Furthermore, González-Pérez and Ramírez-Montoya (2022) delve into the positive effects of integrating ICT in classrooms, illustrating how it enhances learner participation and

Fig. 5. Educational Management Insights in Implementing Innovative Instructional Strategies

stimulates interest in learning. By utilizing technological tools, educators can cultivate vibrant, interactive environments that encourage active participation and cater to individual learning styles. This approach empowers learners to take ownership of their learning, equipping them with the necessary skills to navigate the complexities of the digital world confidently. Lastly, Gudmundsdottir et al. (2020) underscore the importance of integrating digital citizenship into education. They advocate for educators to model responsible technology use, thereby highlighting the need for discussions around online safety, copyright awareness, and respectful communication. By incorporating these elements into the curriculum, teachers foster a sense of responsibility among learners, ensuring they are not only proficient in technology

use but also cognizant of its broader social implications. In summary, embracing learner-centered innovations through these strategies prepares learners for future challenges while nurturing their growth as responsible digital citizens. Overall, learner-centered innovation in kindergarten is essential for engaging young learners and addressing their diverse developmental needs. By incorporating creative instructional strategies and technology, educators can enhance academic, social, and emotional skills while fostering critical thinking and collaboration. Emphasizing digital citizenship within the curriculum ensures that learners not only gain proficiency with technology but also understand its ethical implications, preparing them for responsible participation in a digital world.

4. Implications and Future Directions

In this chapter, the study's summary is presented. I inferred the implications and future directions from the findings of the study. The purpose of my study is to uncover the experiences, coping mechanisms, and educational management insights of the kindergarten teachers in implementing innovative instructional strategies.

4.1. Findings—I employed thematic analysis in conjunction with a qualitative phenomenological approach to accomplish the research goals. To obtain an authentic grasp of people's experiences, open-ended interview questions were used in accordance with Creswell's (2018) recommendations. Additionally, by using this interviewing technique, I encouraged my participants to wholly and freely express how they define or interpret the phenomenon under investigation- the role of innovative instructional strategies in the experiences and narratives of kindergarten teachers. Based on the study's result, the thematic analysis revealed the following emerging themes: the experiences of kindergarten teachers in implementing innovative instructional strategies are resource and technology constraints, time and workload challenges, and creative pedagogy. On the other hand, the emerging themes for the coping mechanisms applied by kindergarten teachers are professional development, collaboration and peer support, and resilience. Lastly, the educational management insights of kindergarten teachers are narrowed to the emerging themes- additional teacher support and learner-centered innovation. The first set of themes emerged from the experiences of kindergarten teachers in implementing innovative instructional strategies. One major challenge identified was resource and technology constraints. Teachers expressed difficulty in accessing adequate resources and technology to integrate innovative strategies into their teaching effectively. These limitations hinder their ability to fully execute creative and practical instruction in the classroom. Another significant challenge was time and workload pressures. Teachers reported that the demands of managing their classroom while also incorporating new strategies often left them with insufficient time to engage with and implement innovative teaching methods fully. The balancing act between meeting curricular requirements and the time needed for planning and executing innovative approaches was a significant hurdle. Creative pedagogy also emerged as a central theme. While teachers expressed enthusiasm for exploring new ways to engage young learners, they acknowledged that the traditional educational structure and constraints sometimes stifled their ability to embrace creativity in teaching fully. Nonetheless, many teachers found ways to inject creativity into their lessons, even within a restrictive environment. The coping mechanisms employed by kindergarten teachers were explored in a second thematic area. The first coping strategy identified was professional development. Teachers emphasized the importance of attending training sessions, workshops, and other opportunities for growth to build the skills necessary to implement innovative strategies effectively. This professional development helped them stay up-to-date with current trends and improve their instructional practices. The second coping mechanism was collaboration and peer support. Teachers often turned to colleagues for support, sharing ideas, strategies, and resources to overcome challenges. Peer collaboration allowed them to learn from one another, create a sense of community, and develop innovative approaches together. Resilience also emerged as a key coping mechanism. Despite the numerous challenges they faced, teachers demonstrated remarkable resilience in their ef-

forts to continue implementing innovative strategies. This resilience was rooted in their commitment to their student's success and their determination to overcome the obstacles in their path. The second, the study revealed insights into educational management from the perspective of kindergarten teachers. One important theme was the need for additional teacher support. Teachers indicated that they would benefit from increased support from school leadership, including more resources, time for professional development, and assistance in managing their workload. Finally, key insight was the empha-

sis on learner-centered innovation. Teachers highlighted the importance of focusing on the individual needs of learners and adapting innovative strategies to fit the learning styles of young children. They believed that a learner-centered approach was essential for fostering creativity, critical thinking, and overall student engagement. These themes highlight both the challenges and opportunities in implementing innovative instructional strategies in early childhood education and provide valuable insights into how educational management can support teachers in this process.

4.2. Implications—The results of my analysis revealed several significant findings related to the experiences, challenges, coping mechanisms, and educational management insights of kindergarten teachers as they implement innovative instructional strategies. The first key implication is that the resource and technology constraints faced by kindergarten teachers are a substantial barrier to the effective implementation of innovative strategies. These limitations hinder teachers' ability to fully integrate new methods and technologies into their teaching practices, potentially impacting the quality of learning experiences for young learners. Educational institutions and policymakers need to prioritize investment in technology and resources to better support teachers in their efforts to innovate and enhance their instructional approaches. Another important implication is the time and workload challenges that teachers face. The demands of managing a classroom, fulfilling administrative tasks, and implementing innovative strategies create significant pressure on teachers, leaving little time for creative planning and reflection. Educational leadership should consider implementing policies that reduce administrative burdens and provide teachers with dedicated time for professional development and instructional planning. This

would enable them to focus more on innovative practices that could benefit their learners. The creative pedagogy employed by teachers also indicates that, despite challenges, there is a strong desire to engage learners in dynamic and innovative learning experiences. However, these efforts are often constrained by traditional structures and a lack of adequate support. There is a need for more flexible curricula, and teaching approaches that foster creativity, allowing teachers to experiment with new methods without being restricted by rigid frameworks. In response to these challenges, kindergarten teachers utilize several coping mechanisms, such as professional development. It underscores the importance of continuous training and education to help teachers stay current with best practices and instructional innovations. Policymakers and educational institutions should invest in ongoing professional development opportunities to enhance teachers' skills, especially in the areas of creative pedagogy and technology integration. Collaboration and peer support also emerged as vital coping strategies. Teachers who collaborate with colleagues can share resources, ideas, and strategies, creating a supportive network that enables them to overcome challenges. Encouraging collaboration among teachers through team-building activities, pro-

professional learning communities, and peer mentoring can foster a culture of support and shared learning, improving the overall teaching environment. Moreover, the theme of resilience highlights the determination of teachers to overcome obstacles despite the challenges they face. This resilience is essential for maintaining high-quality education in the face of adversity. However, resilience alone is not sufficient; systemic support is needed to help teachers sustain their motivation and effectiveness in the classroom. From an educational management perspective, the need for additional teacher support is a critical insight. Teachers need more support from school leadership in terms of resources, professional development, and time for instructional planning. By providing these resources, schools can help teachers implement innovative strategies more effectively, leading to better outcomes for learners. Secondly, the emphasis on learner-

centered innovation suggests that educational management should prioritize student-centered approaches that focus on the individual needs and interests of learners. Teachers believe that a more personalized, learner-centered environment would better support the innovative strategies they wish to implement. This insight calls for a shift in educational management towards supporting practices that prioritize student engagement, creativity, and personalized learning experiences. In conclusion, the study reveals that while kindergarten teachers face significant challenges in implementing innovative instructional strategies, they also exhibit resilience and employ effective coping mechanisms. Educational institutions and policymakers must address the resource, time, and support needs of teachers to create an environment where innovation can thrive, ultimately benefiting both teachers and their learners.

4.3. Future Directions—Based on the study’s findings, it is crucial that the insights gathered are effectively communicated and applied by the key stakeholders for whom this research was intended.

Educational Leaders The study’s findings benefit educational leaders by gaining a deeper understanding of the unique experiences, challenges, and coping mechanisms employed by kindergarten teachers in implementing innovative instructional strategies. With this knowledge, they can develop targeted programs or professional development seminars focused on overcoming resource and technology constraints, time management, and fostering creative pedagogy. These initiatives could equip teachers with the necessary tools to better navigate the complexities of their roles, ultimately leading to more effective teaching and improved student outcomes. **Learners** Another significant benefactor of this study are the learners since this study propounds the utilization of in-

novative instructional strategies. In other words, practical instruction through innovative instructional strategies can be positively associated with improved outcomes for kindergarten learners and their academic performances.

Teachers The focal beneficiary of the study are the teachers themselves. They can use the study’s findings to better understand the challenges they face and the coping mechanisms available to them. Teachers can reflect on how they manage resource limitations, time pressures, and creative demands, and apply the coping strategies such as professional development, collaboration, and resilience in their daily practice. The findings can also help teachers connect with one another to form supportive networks and share best practices for implementing innovative instructional strategies. **School Heads** The findings are valuable to school heads in informing their decision-making processes related to teacher support and resource allocation. The insights gained from this study can

help school heads design more comprehensive and supportive systems for teachers. By recognizing the challenges teachers face, school heads can advocate for more resources, offer better professional development opportunities, and create a more conducive work environment that encourages innovation in teaching. Educational Institutions The findings of the study can further support teachers by enhancing professional development programs and creating a more collaborative environment. Institutions could provide teachers with opportunities to explore and learn from new teaching strategies, improve their knowledge of technology integration, and find ways to implement creative pedagogy despite time and resource constraints.

Future Researchers The study provides a framework for future researchers in conducting quantitative research to explore the prevalence of specific challenges and coping mechanisms

experienced by kindergarten teachers. A more extensive survey could provide numerical data on which coping mechanisms are most effective and how they impact the implementation of innovative instructional strategies. Additionally, future studies could examine the long-term effects of these strategies on both teachers and learners to further deepen the understanding of how innovative practices influence early childhood education. These findings present an opportunity for a collaborative effort among learners, educational leaders, school heads, teachers, and researchers to continue improving the implementation of innovative instructional strategies. By applying these insights, educational systems can better support teachers and create an environment conducive to creative, learner-centered teaching that benefits both educators and learners.

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